

Rape Culture in the Finnish Criminal Justice System.

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Abstract

In recent years, western criminal justice systems have been criticised for their problematic handling of rape cases. Equally, there has been a rising demand from academic circles for these systems to be fundamentally reformed to eliminate attitudes and legislation that perpetuates rape culture. This research project serves as a pilot study aiming to assess the prevalence of rape culture in the Finnish legal system and to explore the potential impact of recent Finnish sex crime legislation. The methodology used in this study is desk-based research. By applying this method, the study juxtaposes precedents from both the Finnish and Swedish Supreme Courts. Sweden was chosen for this comparative analysis because of the similarities between the two countries' criminal justice systems and legislative structures. Moreover, both countries have recently reformed their sex crime legislation.

This project arrives at two main findings. Firstly, the study argues that the Finnish legislative system has contributed negatively to rape culture by legally defining rape through violence or the threat of it. Secondly, the most significant change in recent Swedish sex crime legislation, in terms of challenging rape culture, was the recognition of 'negligent rape'. The project posits that while efforts have been made to eliminate rape culture from the Finnish legal system, there remains room for improvement. Similar to Sweden, the Finnish system could more actively challenge rape culture by criminalising 'negligent rape'. As this research project serves as a pilot study, it provides a foundation for further exploration into the effectiveness of reforms.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

This research project intends to primarily do two things: determine the presence of rape culture in the Finnish criminal system, limiting the scope to Supreme Court instances, and explore the possible impacts that could potentially be expected from the Finnish rape law reform's influence based on the changes in Sweden. Rape culture is mostly perpetuated by the upholding of rape myths, which shape the public and legal receptions and court outcomes of rape complaints. Payne, Lonsway, and Fitzgerald (1999) divided some of the most common rape myths in courts into seven domains and, out of these, two are rather clearly present in the Finnish legal courts: "(2) It wasn't really rape; (3) He didn't mean to" (p. 59). These are, among others, commonly implied attitudes in rape trials, especially when violence was not involved. Finland's sex crime legislation was reformed in 2022 to define rape as consent-based similarly to Sweden's reform in 2018. However, Sweden introduced 'negligent rape' as a criminal offence, which was not implemented in the Finnish rape law. Considering this, it would not be unreasonable to consider the Finnish legal system still relatively unprepared to deal with the variety that rape crimes come in.

The perceptions and definitions of rape have been in a state of flux over the past decade. With increased demand for gender equality and social justice, rape legislations and legal attitudes have been called to implement approaches that minimise and ultimately eliminate the effect of rape culture in the handling of rape crimes. The campaigns and increased awareness of the influence of rape culture have resulted in legislative changes being implemented to minimise the impact (Jokila and Niemi, 2020). In addition to the Finnish and Swedish reforms, Scotland has recently proposed a major legislative change that would eliminate the 'not proven' verdict, which effectively acts as an alternative verdict for 'not guilty' and is thought to play a role in the low rape conviction rate (47%) (Brooks, 2023). These changes and continuing discussion around rape and how it should be policed and penalised to ensure just outcomes display a somewhat internationally shared willingness to recognise the harms of rape and convey the message that these crimes are treated with appropriate seriousness.

While rape myths and their acceptance within the initial encounters with the criminal justice system (CJS) has been studied rather extensively, rape trials in Finland are relatively little researched. Therefore, this research project attempts to address this gap in the literature to the limited degree it is able to. Additionally, because the Finnish sex crime law reform is considerably recent, it is still yet to be subjected to scientific research as there is not yet enough related data to study. By utilising Swedish

Supreme Court precedents as comparison, this research project aims to assess the existing influence of rape culture in the Finnish legal system and, with this juxtaposing, explore the possible impact that the Finnish reform could have. Because this has not been the subject of prior research, this project acts as a pilot study. While this project and its findings are not representative of the CJS and court proceedings in Sweden nor does it attempt to say that this will happen in Finland, it attempts to create a prospective scenario on the potential of the rape law reform.

To assess rape culture's presence in the Finnish legal system, this research project will consider various things. First, rape culture along with the phenomena entailed by it that are relevant for the research will be looked at. These include rape myths generally and a deeper look into the common 'real rape' myth, along with rape myth acceptance. These are followed by the non-physical ways to force and resist in rape cases. Finally, rape legislations in Finland and Sweden will be reviewed along with the Suostumus2018 campaign that led to the Finnish reform, and how the CJSs respond to rape victimisation from the police to legal courts. The review will end with a look into rape statistics to illustrate a picture of how rapes are dealt with in numbers in Finland and Sweden. The analysis will focus on Finnish and Swedish Supreme Court precedents over a collective period of fourteen years (2009-2021). The results of the analysis will be compared in the following ways: Finnish – Swedish (pre-reform); Finnish – Swedish (post-reform); Swedish (pre-reform) – Swedish (post-reform). In this project, it is found that some influence of rape culture can still be detected in the Finnish legal system, and based on the findings, the rape law reform is not expected to have as powerful an impact as it has in Sweden.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

To determine the prevalence of rape culture within CJSs, it is first important to establish what it constitutes. The concept of rape culture is used to illustrate a social environment that normalises and minimises the harms of various forms of sexual violence (O’Neal and Hayes, 2020). It is heavily rooted on values related to sexism and chivalry (Fraser, 2015). Rape culture is ingrained into various societies, and the normalising of sexual violence often stems from attitudes such as ‘boys will be boys’ when engaging in forms of aggressive unwanted sexual touching, implying tolerated male entitlement (Keller, Mendes, and Ringrose, 2018; Stefansen, 2020). Rape culture is especially perpetuated through rape myths and their acceptance that aim to minimise the event by claiming it was unintentional, the woman was ‘asking’ for it, that she enjoyed it, or that the victim lied about their rape due to regret or as an attempt to salvage their reputation (Payne, Lonsway, and Fitzgerald, 1999; Honkatukia, 2001; Grubb and Turner, 2012). One of rape culture’s most prominent by-products can be argued to be the detrimental impact it has on rape victims’ status, experience, and access to support resources and justice.

2.2 Rape Myths

Rape myths is an overarching term used for the pervasive, prejudicial, and stereotyped attitudes and assumptions regarding rape, rape victims and its perpetrators, and the impact of rape victimisation. They stem largely from the traditional sex roles that women and men play in sexual encounters and are argued to create a layer of complexity in the distinction of normal, consensual sexual conduct from sexual violence (Honkatukia, 2001; Egan and Wilson, 2012; Grubb and Turner, 2012; van der Bruggen and Grubb, 2014; O’Neal and Hayes, 2020). These roles provide narrow, pre-laid out scenarios for sexual interactions between women and men that encourage in sexually aggressive behaviours. These scenarios can be argued to present sexual encounters as a chase for men who actively seek out, seduce, and subdue the woman who is expected to provide a challenge but eventually submit. This expectation for women has been found to stem from various beliefs about women’s sexuality, such as an attempt to appear less available to increase appeal as a ‘conquer’, confusion about own sexuality, and secretly wishing to be raped (Honkatukia, 2001; Basow and Minieri, 2011; Egan and Wilson, 2012). By encouraging the ‘chase’ and sexual aggression, rape myths can then be argued to effectively justify rapists’ actions and highlight the victims’ actions in the events as contributing.

Rape myths have historically influenced the distribution of responsibility in rape cases. They represent social values that illustrate women as weak and defenceless, needing of men's protection that is deserved by fulfilling their traditional expectations of femininity. Deviating from these expectations by engaging in 'non-feminine' and 'risky' behaviours, women then seek and deserve their rape victimisation (Grubb and Turner, 2012; O'Neal and Hayes, 2020). Prominent examples of what rape myths consider 'risky' behaviour for women is deliberately consuming alcohol and dressing up in revealing clothes. The engagement in these behaviours has been widely used to justify rape due to rape myths, presenting them as women's way to allure men and initiate the chase. By doing this, women are seen to effectively render men feeble and powerless against their overwhelming desires (Egan and Wilson, 2012; O'Neal and Hayes, 2020). The perseverance of these myths and their employment in the justification of sexually aggressive behaviours indicates a prevalent simultaneous acceptance of unequal gender values and the derogation of women.

The criminalisation of rape and the changes in its definition have been historically contested by the 'real rape' myth endorsed by rape culture. This myth offers a restricted narrative of the crime, parties, and the environment in which rapes take place based on pervasive stereotypes. According to this narrative, rape only happens in a dark, secluded area by a stranger who uses force and armed violence to overpower and rape their verbally and physically resisting victims who are left traumatised and will report the rape immediately to the authorities (Honkatukia, 2001; Grubb and Harrower, 2008; Randall, 2010; Rees, 2010; Bieneck and Krahe, 2011; Immonen-Räihä et al., 2011; van der Bruggen and Grubb, 2014; McGregor, 2016; O'Neal and Hayes, 2020). However, this narrative's sovereignty has been challenged with statistical evidence. Based on reports in Finland, more than half of rapes are committed by an acquaintance of some degree or a friend, while just around every sixth rape was perpetrated by a stranger and 8% of rapes taking place in public places that could potentially match the description (Oikeuspoliittinen Tutkimuslaitos, 2012; Tilastokeskus, 2022). A similar trend can be seen in Sweden, where strangers have been the perpetrators in 25% of recorded rapes (Brå, 2022). However, as previously mentioned, the statistics depict *recorded* rapes, leaving some question on their validity due to these numbers being subject to the influence of underreporting.

Despite the 'real rape' stereotype being challenged as the predominant rape, its prevalence in the CJS can still be perceived due to its employment as a measuring tool when determining the 'realness' of the rape, attribution of responsibility, and victim culpability (Bieneck and Krahe, 2011; van der Bruggen and Grubb, 2014; O'Neal and Hayes, 2020). Rape descriptions and discussions in the CJS still often place considerable weight on the forensically examined physical injuries suffered by the victim to bolster the

prosecution's case (Rees, 2010). Placing such importance on the physical signs of resistance and force leads to failure in recognising any other forms of resistance that might take place, but which are impossible to distinguish with forensic examinations (Randall, 2010). By ignoring other methods of resistance, the rape myth of physical force's prominence is reinforced – the victims are less prone to report their victimisation if they do not have physical injuries to show due to fearing they are going to lack credibility (Egan and Wilson, 2012). As a result of this, the rapes that receive most public and CJS attention are those that include a violent aspect; effectively fading physically non-violent rapes from the general consciousness.

The prevalence and strength of rape myths within a society can be seen in the rate of rape myth acceptance (RMA) which can be argued to be relatively closely tied to the culture in question. This is rather evident as RMA has been found to be higher among men and more broadly, cultures where women are generally devalued and considered as cunning and untrustworthy (Cowan, 2000; van der Bruggen and Grubb, 2014). The prevalence and acceptance of rape myths on various societal and, especially, CJS levels can be argued to create a problematic environment for rape victims. RMA determines the extent of blaming, minimising, and belief the victims are faced with, and it shapes the response offered to rape victims speaking their experience (Grubb and Harrower, 2008; Basow and Minieri, 2011; Grubb and Turner, 2012; van der Bruggen and Grubb, 2014). Accepted rape myths are generally employed as justification for men's sexual violence and aggression, and when the victims are women and girls, this is most often in the form of placing the responsibility on the victim (Egan and Wilson, 2012; Grubb and Turner, 2012; O'Neal and Hayes, 2020). A particularly problematic impact of RMA is the cycle it appears to create; higher RMA has been found to be associated with lowered threshold to commit rape (Grubb and Turner, 2012). This threshold can be argued to be even further lowered if the CJS displays higher levels of RMA and, therefore, treating rapists more leniently.

2.3 Non-Physical Force and Resistance

This chapter will discuss and analyse the non-physical forms of rape that are overlooked within the framework of rape culture. This is to portray an alternative to the physical violence and physical resistance narrative that has historically dominated rape trials and the handling of rapes. Furthermore, its purpose is to introduce these underrepresented forms of rape to create an understanding of the crime's diversity to effectively analyse these types' treatment in courts.

The expectation and overrepresentation of physical violence in rapes recognises only one form of rape, overshadowing a considerable portion of rapes that do not involve the physical forms of coercion and

resistance. Firstly, most legislations appear to recognise physical force and violence as an instrumental part of criminally condemned rape (Western, 2004). Coercion, however, comes in various forms that are not immediately physically violent. These forms are often overlooked in rape trials. The use of threat and intimidation as instruments of rape can be argued to be rather complex as the focus in criminalising threats in rape appears to be on what the immediate health risk is. Any threats of death or severe physical harm and pain are so closely associated with perpetrated physical injuries that rapes involving these elements have been criminalised in various legislations across the world (Western, 2004). This somewhat aligns with the 'real rape' myth due to the high possibility of the serious violence that the myth expects from rapes. However, more abstract threats with psychological and social impact are not perceived as equally condemning as threats of violence and are significantly less represented in jurisdictions (Western, 2004). Perpetrators may, for example, exploit access to any sentimental possessions of the victims' or their ability to exclude the victim from their social events and circles (Western, 2004).

Secondly, resistance in rape cases is often an instinctive reaction to the threatening situation and it can manifest in varying ways. These ways are considerably often not physical and instead include verbal and mentally distancing self-preservation tactics to survive the situation with minimal injuries. Victims may attempt to appeal to the perpetrator by means of negotiating or pretending unconsciousness to either get out of the encounter or to minimise its acute danger. Alternatively, they might seek to discourage the perpetrator by pretending to have a male partner nearby, presenting the perpetrator with an apparent threat (Honkatukia, 2001; Randall, 2010). More prominently, Möller, Söndergaard, and Helström (2017) found humans to have a self-defence mechanism similar to animals that employs a state of temporary natural paralysis called tonic immobility (TI) as a response to a severe threat. This was reported as the response of 70% of woman respondents who had experienced sexual assault. Almost half of these reports included extreme TI (Möller, Söndergaard, and Helström, 2017). The reality of non-physically violent forms of rape being evidently rather common challenges the prevailing 'real rape' myth. However, by not accounting for these forms in jurisdictions and thus rape trials, the CJSs can be argued to contribute to the perseverance of rape culture.

2.4 Rape Legislation & Reform in Finland and Sweden

To meaningfully analyse the prevalence of rape culture in the Finnish legal system, it is important to first understand two vital points in Finnish legislation on rape: its current form, and how this current form has been achieved. The juridical underpinning of rape is mainly built on the baseline understanding of rape as a penetrative sexual act committed without the consent of one party. This

understanding, however, can be argued to be subject to various interpretations and layers of complexity in different jurisdictions. *The Istanbul Convention 2011* recognises rape as a serious form of offending and defines consent as the product of free will (Council of Europe, 2011). While it is an internationally recognised convention, its definition of rape has not been fully adapted to individual countries. Furthermore, the notion of placing consent in the middle of rape legislation has been criticised earlier by Tadros (2006), who claimed it is too confusing and open for interpretations. This approach can be argued to have been present in the Nordic countries as well, and while consent has theoretically been in the centre of rape legislations, proving its lacking has traditionally solely relied on the proof for the use or threat of use of force (Lappi-Seppälä, 2012). This expectation has resulted in a considerable underrepresentation of rape occurrence due to the pressure on victims to show physical proof for their rape either deterring them from reporting or their allegations not being perceived as likely (FRA, 2014). However, this expectation has been challenged in the late years as rape law reforms have taken place in various Nordic countries, including Finland (Jokila and Niemi, 2020).

Finland's rape law has undergone multiple reforms in the last decade, slowly directing the centre of the legislation towards freely given consent. The initial reform in 2011 brought the rape laws that were internationally considered harsh somewhat closer to the standards of international justice by applying a second set of characteristics that would be used to show rape: victim's inability to defend oneself (Amnesty International, 2019a). However, later in 2014, another reform introduced a new, mitigated rape form – coercion to sexual intercourse – that did not require the proof of use or threat of violence but in return yielded a more lenient punishment (Amnesty International, 2019a). This can be argued to have perpetuated rape culture in the Finnish criminal system that appeared to consider rape a crime that is fundamentally defined by the presence of physical violence by separating non-physical rapes entirely into their own category that does not share the term. Even after their reforms, the rape laws were widely criticised for their lack of consideration for consent as a product of free will, eventually inspiring a campaign that would later lead into the most comprehensive rape law reform in the near Finnish history (Suostumus2018, 2018; Amnesty International, 2019a). The campaign entailed the reform of Finnish rape laws that would subsequently be a major advance in minimising the impact of rape culture from the CJS.

The citizen campaign Suostumus2018 (Consent2018) called for a wide reform in the rape law legislation and demonstrated widespread support within the population and political field for the effort to minimise the impact of rape culture in the CJS. Suostumus2018's goal was to bring the legal definition in Finland to correspond to that described in *the Istanbul Convention 2011*. Its main critique was

concerned with the lack of consideration for the diversity of rape and non-consenting sexual intercourse, raising issues of non-physically violent resistance and force to the conversation (Suostumus2018, 2018). The campaign was created and supported by individuals, citizens', students and youths' unions, and various political parties to bring awareness and support for the petition, which eventually got to over 55,000 signatures in December 2018 and subsequently proceeded for Governmental consideration (Suostumus2018, 2018). This consideration later became an accepted Governmental Proposal for a full reform of the *Chapter 20 of the Criminal Code of Finland* with a goal to show the effort to eradicate rape culture from the CJS and, ultimately, discourage prospective rapists and encourage victim reporting (GP 13/2022). While the results of the reform are yet to be seen, the enactment of the reformed rape law displayed the willingness to eradicate rape culture from the Finnish CJS.

In 2022, the Government Proposal to reform sex crime legislation was passed by the Parliament of Finland, removing the essentiality of proving physical injuries to determine rape (GP 13/2022). The new legislation emphasises the role of consent as a central factor in rape cases, whereas before consent was merely an implied aspect that was tied to the lack or presence of physical coercion and resistance (Jokila and Niemi, 2020). This legislative approach had been earlier adapted in Sweden since the Swedish rape law reform in 2018 (Jokila and Niemi, 2020). While both legislations used to rely on the show of futile resistance and physical force as starting points for considerations of rape, the same factors and suddenness of the event are now considered to immediately nullify the possibility of having consented (*Criminal Code of Finland 1889/39; Criminal Code of Sweden 1962/700*). The Swedish reform was met with controversial opinions that were rather consistent with the alignment of rape myth acceptance. Sveriges Radio had conducted a questionnaire on how people perceived the new rape legislation, which was overwhelmingly supported by women (90%) and considerably less by men (62%). Conversely, the reform was evaluated as a negative change by every fifth male respondent (Riddestedt, 2018).

These reforms provide a more abstract and situation-based approach to discussing rape crimes while eliminating some of the pressure the complainants might feel if their experiences did not involve physical force and were rather influenced by fear and/or self-preservation. This is done by removing unclarity in determining consent that have been present in case law, which has previously claimed to be consent-based but where the determination has been heavily reliant on the proof of physical violence (GP 13/2022). Despite the aim to lower the threshold to report rape victimisation, Sweden has not seen a notable increase in the reported rape rate that was already in a steadily increasing trend prior to the reform (Brå, 2022). Therefore, the increase cannot reasonably be argued to be attributed

to the broadened definition of rape that highlights the role of consent, but rather to the increasing general awareness of rape and its various forms. On the other hand, the decreasing trend on cleared rapes in Sweden was turned around after the enactment of the reformed rape law (Brå, 2018). Cleared rapes in this refer to reported rapes where an investigating authority made the decision to close the case – leaving ambiguity over the final state of the investigation and whether a prosecution was made. Due to the new rape law in Finland being enacted from January 2023, similar statistics are not yet available.

2.5 Rape in the Criminal Justice System

Rape crimes can be argued to receive somewhat varying treatments in the Finnish CJS. The processing of rape crimes averaged at 312 days in 2021, which is partially due to both slow reporting times and delays in the investigation process (Tilastokeskus, 2021). This chapter will analyse the efforts and attitudes displayed by the CJSs towards rape victims and how the legislations are applied in practice. The initial attitudes from the CJS are among the most important factors in determining the victims' likelihood to report rape victimisation, and the fear of prejudice and victim-blame displayed by the authorities along with poor effort are among the main deterrents of reporting (Grubb and Turner, 2012). By looking at how CJSs initially respond to rape victimisation from both perspectives of officials and victims, it is possible to determine the presence of underlying attitudes. Furthermore, it provides an opportunity to look for reasons for the underrepresentation of rapes in the CJS in Finland.

2.5.1 Police and Rape

The current Finnish CJS responses to rape victimisation appear still somewhat unprepared to understand rape and how to effectively police it and face the victims appropriately. Public views and attitudes are displayed within the police. This is especially portrayed in the suspicion toward rape victims that largely stems from the belief that false allegations dominate rape complaints. In reality, their quantity is considerably overestimated, and account for a marginal portion of rape cases (Grubb and Turner, 2012; O'Neal and Hayes, 2020). Additionally, Isotalo (2022) highlights the role of the perceptions of vulnerability and power roles within relationships in the ways in which the police understand and articulate rape. The perceptions appear largely determined by the extent to which the victim expresses their unwillingness and experience pressure in their victimisation (Isotalo, 2022). Therefore, the perceptions they can be argued to align with rape culture's stereotypes to an extent, displaying some level of inadequacy in terms of handling sex crimes, including rapes. Furthermore, the Deputy Chancellor of Justice in Finland reported multiple incidents since 2017 in which rape cases had been largely neglected by halting pre-trial investigations for some few years. Although the limits posed

by resources are partially responsible, a considerable number was found to be due to negligence by the officers in charge (Apulaisoikeuskansleri, 2022). The interpretations of the Finnish police in terms of rape victimisation and the handling of such crimes can be argued to display some levels of still prevailing rape culture and unwillingness to investigate them.

Despite these shortcomings, the CJS cannot be entirely blamed for a lack of attempt to understand rape and its complexities. In their interview study, Isotalo (2022) distinguished three different styles in which police officers articulated rape victims, with one dubbed as the “victim sensitive vernacular” (p. 276). This style is described to recognise the difficulties in expressing their lack of consent, especially within young people who might lack the tools to identify and express their own sexuality (Isotalo, 2022). Amnesty International (2019b) reported some rape victims in Finland to have experienced positive treatment from the police officers responding to their reports. Positively evaluated reports commonly included the consideration for the victim’s own pace in the process, explaining the victim the interviews’ purposes and procedures, and actively avoiding victim-blaming (Amnesty International, 2019b). In the same report, a further measure was highlighted in Sweden where a complainant’s counsel had been introduced since the 2018 law reform to act as a support for the victim and a quality-enhancing body in the investigation process (Amnesty International, 2019b). Despite the presence of some rape culture in the Finnish police service, the efforts to overcome this phenomenon can be witnessed in the positive victim experiences. However, there is still some distance to the effort displayed in Sweden to ensure the justice and safety of rape victims.

2.5.2 Rape in Courts

Criminal courts still appear to somewhat preserve rape culture-positive practices. This is especially visible within the prevailing idea that rape victims should be able to show they have been victims of ‘real rape’, and basing decisions on the assessment of consent as an abstract concept can be argued to be both alien and insufficient. The prosecution’s success is often reliant on the victim’s ability to show physical proof that has been verified by forensic medical examiners (FME) to prove the lack of consent, and convictions’ likelihood appears to increase with the severity and quantity of physical injuries (Randall, 2010; Rees, 2010; van der Bruggen and Grubb, 2014; Jokila and Niemi, 2020). Although this cannot be considered entirely unreasonable due to the presumption of innocence, which is a fundamental right in the European Union (*Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union 2012*). However, in some cases, proving the occurrence of physical violence is not enough to constitute a lack of consent and can be treated as ‘rough’ sex with consent (Honkatukia, 2001). The complexities in determining consent can therefore be argued to exceed the abstractness of solely discussing consent

as a conceptual expression. It appears discussing consent is consistently rather nuanced and lacking in ambiguity within court proceedings.

The inconsistency of criminal justice processes and attitudes can be argued to make reporting somewhat of a gamble for the victims, contributing to the underreporting of the crime. Amnesty International (2019b) found Finnish rape victims to have considerably mixed experiences in their respective rape trials. The court personnel's attitudes ranged widely from displaying high degrees of RMA to humane and supportive manners, and the most positive experiences had included feelings of being heard and supported. In some cases, the victims reported relatively neutral experiences where the same seriousness was applied to both complainant and the defendant. In the cases with most rape culture-positive attitudes present throughout the legal process, some victims even described the process as more traumatising than the rape itself (Amnesty International, 2019a; Amnesty International, 2019b). Similar points have been found in Sweden, where the emphasis on the importance of improving the quality of rape crime interviews was made internally by the Director of the Public Prosecutions. Meanwhile, Finland has been externally demanded to see to the removal of rape culture in its CJS (Amnesty International, 2019a; Amnesty International, 2019b). These widely altering attitudes when facing rape victims and crimes can be argued to deter rape victims from reporting the crimes, creating a considerable gap in not only in crime statistics but also in the efforts to effectively police and deter crime.

2.5.3 Official Rape Statistics

Rape is generally portrayed as a rare form of offending that only impacts a fraction of the population. By looking at sources outside the national crime statistical bulletins, a discrepancy can be witnessed between what is reported to the authorities and what is reported to other bodies. In 2021, 1,851 rapes were reported to the authorities in Finland – an average of approximately 154 rape reports every month (Tilastokeskus, 2022). However, Victim Support Finland (RIKU) received just over 900 monthly calls from rape victims (Malin, Vauhkonen, and Latvala, 2022). Meanwhile, out of the over 27,600 sex offences committed in Sweden in 2021, 9,962 were classified as rape, 9,026 of which were committed against women (Brå, 2022). Despite Sweden's population being almost twice the size to that of Finland, the occurrence of rape was almost ninefold in Sweden in 2021. While there is not a considerable increase in the reported rapes in Sweden compared to Finland, an argument can be made that rape victims in Finland are likely somewhat more deterred to report their victimisation.

In the National Crime Survey (KRT) conducted in Finland in 2021, 3,2% of the woman respondents reported to having been forced or attempted to be forced to participate in sexual intercourse against their will within the year prior to taking the survey (Malin, Vauhkonen, and Latvala, 2022). Out of the 4,813 respondents of KRT in 2021, 2,687 were women – meaning that approximately 8,5 women in 100 had been raped within the year leading up to the questionnaire (Kolttola and Näsi, 2022). In Finland, where almost three million citizens are women, this number would translate to more than 200,000 rapes against women during that year, which is a considerably higher number than those reported to the authorities. In the Swedish National Security Survey (NTU), approximately 1,2% of women reported they had been victims of rape crimes (Brå, 2022). This would translate to over 600,000 rapes against women in that year. However, while police reports fail to represent the true occurrence of rapes due to many victims not reporting, these self-report surveys are very limited in scale. This should be considered in the interpretation process as it is impossible for these surveys to account for regional differences and to gather the samples in a way that fully represents the prevalence of specific crimes, especially rape.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The main purpose of this research project is to examine the prevalence of rape culture within the Finnish CJS decision-making regarding rape crimes. In this framework, the project aims to determine whether and how rape culture can be considered to influence decision-making regarding rape cases within the CJS. Furthermore, the project seeks out to answer the following questions:

1. Is *the Istanbul Convention's 2011* defining feature of rape – lack of consent – factually sufficient for criminal condemnation?
2. How is consent perceived in criminal justice systems?
3. What can the Finnish legal system learn from the Swedish reform?

To achieve this, secondary research using a desk-based approach was chosen as the most appropriate and effective method. This included the use of Finnish and Swedish Supreme Court precedents. The main reason why these precedents were chosen over lower court instance documents was their availability; all precedents are public and available for anyone to look up. This eliminated the extensive and potentially costly application process of accessing similar documents in lower court instances that require an extra layer of protection and anonymity due to them involving identifying information. However, due to this, the available documents ended up being limited in quantity since only a fraction of appeals made in Finland and Sweden end up being accepted and heard in the Supreme Courts.

Due to the limits posed by both available data and the extent of this research project, the number of precedents was limited to eight precedents from both Finland Sweden respectively. A rough typology was then created for the purpose of this research, and the precedents were divided into "real rape' myth compliant cases' and "real rape' myth non-compliant cases' based on the prosecution's description of the rape. This division was based on violence being central in both the 'real rape' myth, and especially Finnish rape legislation prior to the reform. Swedish precedents were also divided into pre-reform and post-reform categories to analyse the influence of the reform. Due to the recent reform in Finnish rape legislation, the analysis consists of older cases, and parallels are drawn from the differences exhibited in Swedish precedents and the changes in them.

Desk-based research includes the use of pre-existing documents instead of conducting primary research. Choosing this approach ensured the collection of data without needing to navigate the ethical dilemmas related to both gathering data and exposing participants to the sensitive and traumatic topic of rape. Desk-based approach is also useful due to it removing both time and effort that would be consumed by conducting primary research (Crowther-Dowey and Fussey, 2013). However, the use of existing documents introduces the issue of suitability of the documents to answer the questions (Yar, 2018). This was considered by creating and altering the questions to both suit the purpose and the documents available. This research project also recognises that politics and values can potentially steer both the direction of choosing the topic and methodology in social science research (Clark et al., 2021). In this project, the topic was chosen due to a personal interest in the Finnish rape legislation and especially what kind of impact it could potentially be expected to have based on the reform's impact on Sweden. Any bias in choosing the methodology and precedents were attempted to avoid by choosing cases based on the topic word 'rape' and choosing all corresponding precedents from the chosen time periods.

The value and integrity of social science research is predominantly rooted in its ethical considerations. This research project conforms to the ethical guidelines outlined by the British Criminological Society (BCS, 2015) and the British Sociological Association (BSA, 2017). These guidelines are laid out to ensure the research's integrity, fulfilled responsibilities towards the field of criminology, colleagues, and participants, as well as the safety for anyone involved in the research process. This project also seeks to fully recognise itself as only a student research project with limited time and resources to avoid misinterpretation of the grounds on which any arguments are made. While the project attempts to be as objective as possible, it also recognises the difficulty of full objectivity in scientific research as suggested in Diener and Crandall (1978).

Chapter 4: Analysis on Supreme Court Precedents

4.1 Supreme Courts in Finland and Sweden

In the CJSs of Finland and Sweden, Supreme Court instances are the highest and final ones in hearing criminal matters, and their interpretations hold considerable legislative weight in future proceedings (Supreme Court of Finland, 2020; Supreme Court of Sweden, 2022). The main purpose of Supreme Courts is to interpret and create precedents in cases that are beyond direct applications of law. The focus of interpretation often targets on a specific factor in either the crime or proceeding in a previous instance, such as mistake, that is considered meaningful to uphold the cohesiveness of case law but to which the law does not provide a clear answer. These precedents can then be used as a guide in all court instances navigating similar cases in the future (Supreme Court of Finland, 2020; Supreme Court of Sweden, 2022). The Supreme Courts only hear cases through appeals process and they hear approximately 100 cases yearly. Out of these, 1% are rape crimes in Finland and 5% in Sweden (Supreme Court of Finland, 2020; Supreme Court of Sweden, 2022). The small number of rape cases heard makes it impossible to draw representative patterns and deductions from both the outcomes and themes present in the proceedings.

4.2 Finnish Supreme Court

In the analysed Finnish Supreme Court (Korkein Oikeus, KKO) precedents, rape hearings were primarily focused on evaluating the presented proof and whether it is enough to prevent any reasonable doubt on the defendant's guilt. By focusing on the point of evaluation, these hearings can be argued to overlook the concept of consent as a product of free will which, however, was not a legal concept in the Finnish legislation at the time of these precedents. In some instances, this has led to the acquittal of the defendant while somewhat recognising the non-consensual nature of the intercourse. The evaluations are largely concerned with the *intentionality* of the defendant, not whether consent was given or not. This is most often based the threat and/or the apparently premeditated decision to exploit the complainants' defenceless state. The focus on intentionality and proof of physical violence can be argued to endorse a limited perception of rape that is foremost based on the 'real rape' myth, which can be argued to be still considered somewhat of an expectation for these crimes. However, due to the very limited number of precedents used in the analysis, no representative claims can be made – rather, they should be considered indicative of how rape perceptions can vary.

4.3 'Real Rape' Myth Compliant & Non-Compliant Cases

The rape's provable proximity to the 'real rape' myth can be argued to be a somewhat considerable factor in the outcome of the hearing. Three (37,5%) of the analysed KKO precedents in Finland involved the use or threat of physical violence in the prosecution's description for the crime. Forensic evidence for physical violence is considered some of the most important proof in rape trials (Rees, 2010), and this importance was present in the analysed precedents. Two of the hearings reached a guilty verdict in the SC, and in both, the prosecution's case was strengthened with evidence of the extensive injuries that the complainants suffered during their rapes (KKO:2019:84; KKO:2014:91). Conversely, the one precedent that had resulted in the acquittal of the defendant, the prosecution had no physical evidence of injuries or coercion, but rather, the complainant's training psychotherapist whom she was a practice patient of, gave their testimony (KKO:2021:44). While documented and impartial evidence is crucial for reaching a verdict, based on these cases it can be argued that lack of consent alone was not enough for rape conviction in Finland where rape can be argued to be foremost about violence.

Some variety in the ways consent is discussed and highlighted in the precedents can be seen based on the apparent presence of physical coercion and violence. The perception of consent being too unambiguous to be a central concept in legislation is widely present in the Finnish legislation where it is often only brought up and discussed as supplemental to violent rapes. This was highlighted in KKO:2021:44, which was fully concerned with whether the intercourse had been consensual or forced, yet the discussion on consent was mostly focused on the probability of the violent coercion. The lack of physical evidence entailed the overlooking of the documented psychological symptoms that were concluded typical for a victim of sex crime and could potentially indicate the non-consensual nature of the intercourses. On the other hand, in both KKO:2019:84 and KKO:2014:91, the extensive evidence for grievous violence presented by the prosecution resulted in the court highlighting the fact that the intercourses clearly lacked consent. In these cases, the complainant's freezing (TI) and passivity were not seen as consenting to the acts or mitigating. Based on these findings, rather than being its own concept, consent can be argued to be tied to the amount of violence, fear, and physical coercion in Finnish legal understandings.

The effective unimportance of consent is further visible within the differences between hearings of cases that involved violence and cases that did not. Five (62,5%) of the precedents in the analysis did not involve violence or physical coercion in the description and out of these, only one resulted in a guilty verdict in the KKO. Similarly to the violent cases, this conviction was reached with documented professional and impartial evidence. This was the DNA evidence taken from both parties the day

following the event, and it supported the complainant's story (KKO:2021:31). While it is obvious that landing a verdict requires supportive evidence, these precedents can be argued to show that consent has not necessarily been a main concern in the analysed hearings. In three other precedents, the complainants are recognised to initially not having consented at all and/or being unable to do effectively do so. The recognised inabilities have included a disability that causes weaker cognitive ability, being asleep, and being heavily intoxicated (KKO:2022:71; KKO:2019:55; KKO:2019:78). In these cases, lack of consent was not seen as a condemning factor due to the evaluation on the intentionality of the defendants reaching the conclusion that their intention was not to rape the complainant.

The perceptions of consent can be argued to be considerably different when the complainant has not been coerced into intercourse on threat or use of violence. Contrary to their violent counterparts in the analysis, the non-violent rape precedents mostly depicted passivity and TI as a form of consenting – even when the complainants had been simultaneously deemed unable to give reasonable consent. If the complainants had displayed any initiative to the intercourse – such as after a longer discussion on whether the intercourse is going to happen such as in KKO:2022:71 or when the complainant was considered effectively too intoxicated to consent in KKO:2019:78, it was perceived as effective consent in the hearings. Another interesting conclusion on consent was in KKO:2022:50, where the complainant's account and claim to not having consented was deemed untrustworthy due to her clear memory of the event despite having been heavily intoxicated. Meanwhile, the defendant's account of consensual intercourse was seen as enough to cast reasonable doubt on the claims despite admitting to not being able to remember specific encounters due to seeing so many women. The varying perceptions of consent in the analysed precedents can be argued to imply that Finnish rape trials are fundamentally concerned with the violent aspects of the potential rapes. However, due to the limited number of precedents in this analysis, this argument cannot be considered representative but rather it should be taken as suggestive to a potentially present issue in the legal system.

4.4 Swedish Supreme Court

Contrary to the Finnish precedents, the analysed Swedish Supreme Court (Högsta Domstolen, HD) precedents display more evaluation of somewhat unambiguous and legally grey aspects within the rapes and more often recognised the rape as having happened and rather measure appropriate sentences. This was especially the case after the 2018 reform, which appeared to place consent more towards the centre of the hearings. Prior to the reform, the precedents can be argued to have displayed somewhat similar overlooking of consent as a factor in rape instances as was present in the Finnish precedents. Despite the similarities especially within the evaluation of intentionality, the precedents

displayed higher levels of neutrality toward both parties compared to Finland, and the outcomes were rather divided with acquittals and guilty verdicts reaching similar representation throughout the analysed precedents. Due to the very limited number of precedents in the analysis, it is unreasonable and impossible to draw representative conclusions based on this analysis alone, however, it does suggest a considerable difference in the role and perceptions of consent resulting from the 2018 reform.

4.5 Before the Reform: ‘Real Rape’ Myth Compliant & Non-Compliant Cases

In contrast to the Finnish precedents, even before the 2018 reform the Swedish ones can be argued to have been less concerned with how the alleged rapes align with the ‘real rape’ myth’s narrative. The main discussion of B 1867-09 was concerned with physical evidence of being held at knifepoint. Despite the complainant calling the SOS alarm – implying some level of distress – the lack of any evidence of the scenario was considered enough to cast considerable doubt on the reality of the rape, resulting in the acquittal of the defendant. However, in such a serious accusation, the expectation of concrete proof would be reasonable. Conversely, in B 3277-15, the focus of the hearing was more toward the actions of the defendant that were confirmed by other people present at the scene. In this case, the defendant was found guilty of rape despite the lack of clear evidence of violence. The differing narratives and focuses of these two cases can be argued to represent a relatively unambiguous system that was attempting to emphasise on the violent aspects less of rape yet was still somewhat contained by the current legislation that associated rapes with force.

The differences between the analysed precedents display both differing perceptions and levels of discussion for consent. In B 1867-09, consent is not discussed in the hearing, and it is overlooked due to the focus on the existence of the knife used to coerce the intercourse. While this could suggest the possibility of lying about being held at knifepoint to increase believability by appearing as a victim of a ‘real rape’, it would be unreasonable to make such conclusions with the limited information available. B 3277-15, however, highlights that while the complainant’s consent is somewhat tied to the force used to coerce the intercourse, the testimonies of other people being harassed can be argued to indicate that all the instances are recognised as non-consensual. Therefore, at least in Swedish HD, the perceptions of consent can be argued to be as central and tied to the violent aspects of the rapes as they have been in Finland. Still, while the non-consensual nature might be recognised in violently described rapes, it appears to not have been sufficient for conviction in the analysed HD cases.

Aligning with the findings on the compliant cases, in non-compliant cases, consent was varyingly discussed and held significance of considerable variety. In these cases, proof of some form of resistance or coercion to show consent was not given was relatively more central than it appeared to be in the cases that corresponded more to the 'real rape' myth's narrative. In B 1013-09, while the complainant's mother's testimony on the complainant's behaviour aligned with her account of being raped, the court could not rule a guilty verdict based solely on this testimony and the complainant's memory of the event. On the other hand, in B 1432-16, the complainant's inability to consent due to substance use was considered evident from the beginning of the hearing. The court did not require further proof of resistance or force, likely partially due to the complimenting drug-related crimes the defendant was also on trial for and the involvement of another person in the rape. These precedents present a rather different approach to non-violent rape crimes than that present in Finland. However, it can be argued that in these cases consent is still technically not as important as *the Istanbul Convention 2011* suggests it should be.

Rather similarly to the case of Finland, the differences in how consent is perceived can be argued to be somewhat tied to the presented proof of the event. While consent is not centrally discussed in B 1013-09, the complainant's story is considered fully believable with the supplemental testimony on the complainant's behaviour change after the event. However, while the court does not take a stand on whether consent was given or not, it is not ruled as rape due to the inability to present further evidence. Consent was, however somewhat discussed in B 1432-16, where the complainant's unconsciousness was not considered as consenting. Rather, her state was seen as completely defenceless, warranting an aggravated rape verdict for the defendant for the exploitation of this state. Rather than in the Finnish courts that also required threat or use of force, these Swedish precedents can be argued to discuss consent considerably less. Despite these findings, due to the limits posed by the amounts of cases, they are not to be taken as representative of the Swedish legal system prior to the 2018 reform. Rather, they indicate to the existence of inconsistencies in the system that were acknowledged in the reform.

4.6 After the Reform: 'Real Rape' Myth Compliant & Non-Compliant Cases

The impact of the 2018 reform can be seen in the analysed cases to some extent, however, the limited understanding of more modern relationships and the role of consent can still be argued to influence these instances. The use of knife and the fear imposed to coerce the complainant, along with the complainant having had been asleep prior to the rape in B 6401-21 were more discussed than the lack of consent. While this mostly due to the charge being aggravated rape that requires the use of violence

or threat of it, this could have potentially been the course of the hearing for a baseline rape prior to the reform. However, in B 779-21, despite the court acknowledging the defendant's violence, the complainant's reported lack of consent did not suffice to reach a guilty verdict despite the new legislation being consent-based. This was mostly based on the court's notion that the sexual relationship between the parties entailed the inability of the defendant to reasonably see that the complainant did not consent at the moment. While the reform did cause major changes in the legislation, the analysed cases on cases described as violent appear to not have considerable improvement in terms of the role of consent in the case. However, it should be noted as well that one case being tried as aggravating rape could not be centred around consent due to the different legal requirements.

While the changes in perceptions of consent entailed by the reform are somewhat present in the analysed cases, they create a layer of complexity in the hearings. In B 6401-21, the victim was not considered to consent at any point, and passivity and TI were not treated as having consented. The use of knife to coerce the intercourse was deemed furthering the blameworthiness, indicating the recognition of a lack of consent that would have alone constituted a baseline rape. However, the complexity is more prominent in B 779-21, where it was concluded that the complainant had not consented, and similarly to the second case, TI was not perceived as consenting to the act. Due to the evaluation of intentionality, the TI was somewhat considered to contribute to the defendant's inability to recognise the complainant's withdrawn consent. Therefore, it could be argued that while the new legislation emphasises the perception of consent in rape cases as an abstract product of free will, it can still lack in some of its applications, potentially resulting in the acquittal of defendants while recognising that consent had not been given.

The influence of the 2018 reform is the most visible in the analysed non-violent rape hearings, which place consent in a considerably more central role. This is especially present in the first verdict of negligent rape in B 1200-19, which was fully based on the notions of the complainant who had not consented to the sexual acts. The court placed great emphasis on the complainant's prior text messages claiming to not want a sexual encounter, and later not actively consenting during the act. Similarly, in B 2862-20, the question was about lowering the sentence rather than whether the instance was rape. The focus was mostly on the blameworthiness of the defendant while still recognising that the intercourse had been non-consensual. While the sentence was lowered, it was not due to considering the encounter consensual. These changes are a considerable difference to the pre-reform

considerations, and the current legislation can be argued to better reflect rape as a consent-based crime.

A considerable alteration resulting from the reform is the perception of consent changing to its abstract, product of a free will form and placing greater emphasis on it. This was especially highlighted in B 1200-19, where the parties were acquainted and spent the night together, yet the complainant's passivity and TI were not considered as consenting, and the court concluded that the defendant should have been aware of this. This can be argued to display considerable development in terms of understanding rape crimes and adapting the legislation to better correspond to the crime's nature. In B 2862-20, while the sentence was lowered, this was not due to perceiving the intercourse as consensual. Despite the complainant having initially consented, it was only seen to encompass the specific sexual act consented to, and the court concluded that other acts were not under the same consent. These perceptions differ considerably from both pre-reform Swedish precedents and Finnish precedents. While this cannot be considered a representative sample of the Swedish legal system or even the HD, these findings can be argued to imply a distinctive change in the legal climate regarding rape crime and the role of consent in Sweden.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

Based on the critical analysis on the Supreme Court precedents in both Finland and Sweden in the light of *the Istanbul Convention 2011*, rape culture can be argued to be at least somewhat prevalent in the Finnish legal system prior to the sex crime law reform. The legal system has historically perceived rapes with a 'real rape' myth's underpinning, resulting in misunderstanding and undermining rape and its victims, eventually causing the reluctance to report and distortion of rape statistics. The Finnish legislation received international criticism for the weight it gave to violence over consent in rape cases, and this weighing was noticeably present in the analysed precedents. The biggest sign of rape culture's influence in the Finnish legislation could then be argued to be embedded in the preservation of the requirement of violence or threat of it in rape cases. While the legislation also recognises the exploitation of defenceless state as incriminating, the perceived *intention to exploit* was somewhat tied to the proximity to the 'real rape' narrative, namely how acquainted the parties were. This manifested as the perception of passivity and TI more often as consenting in acquaintance rape cases. While limited in number, the hearings indicate the possibility of prevalence of rape culture within Finnish KKO. However, by accepting the initiative and completely reforming the sex crime legislation and, therefore, legislation on rape, the Finnish legal system appears to have taken a considerable step to eradicate rape culture's influence.

The findings on Swedish HD precedents can be argued to be somewhat indicative in terms of how the Finnish sex crime law reform could potentially influence rape trials. The legal systems and legislations are rather similar, and in the analysis, some similar aspects were present in the Finnish and pre-reform Swedish precedents. The considerable differences in especially non-violent rapes in Swedish HD pointed to a notable impact made by the reform, mostly due to the introduction of 'negligent rape'. By completely reforming the legislation to centre around consent as an abstract concept and criminalising negligence in sexual encounters, the Swedish legal system has been able to reduce rape culture's influence, especially in how consent and responsibility are perceived in rape cases. However, the Swedish legal system's success in minimising the impact of rape culture in the analysed HD hearings reveals a notable gap in the Finnish reform: the lack of 'negligent rape'. While negligence is often present in the *Criminal Code of Finland 1889/39*, it does not allow for rape conviction. This could be argued to have potential to result in the rape culture integrating to the evaluation of intentionality.

It is argued in this project that rape culture can somewhat be seen to influence the CJS decision-making regarding rape, at least on the highest court instance level. However, it recognises and appreciates the presumption of innocence in the legal systems, and the burden of proof falling on the prosecution in any criminal cases. While the criminal court instances are primarily reliant on evidence to issue a verdict, it can be argued to create a problem when the courts determine whether consent was given or not. Especially with a distinct phenomenon such as rape culture potentially impacting the values of a society and CJS, it can be easy to make assumptions of what happened in the case based solely on the level of violence and coercion. Therefore, the ruling of rape cases would be easier – simply comparing it to the ‘real rape’ myth’s narrative removes a considerable amount of effort in determining the criminality in the cases. On the other hand, the denial of non-violent rapes and their impact on the people contradicts with the freedom of personal integrity and liberty claimed in the *Constitution of Finland 1999/731* which prohibits treatment that violates human dignity.

As a final remark, it is recognised that this is a student research paper with an extremely limited range of analysed sources. Therefore, all the conclusions and arguments made in this paper have been based on whether the analysed precedents can be considered to indicate the presence of a potentially larger-scale issue within the legal system. While the analysed precedents have been gathered from the highest-level court instances, they do not represent the systems as a whole – in fact, they only represent a fraction of rape trials that take place in Finland and Sweden yearly. However, due to the findings indicating to some possibility of rape culture’s continuing prevalence in the Finnish legal system, it would be an interesting topic for further research to determine whether the new legislation succeeds in minimising rape culture’s influence and what could further be learned from Sweden.

References

Amnesty International (2019a) Oikeuksien Arpapel: Naisiin Kohdistuvat Raiskausrikokset ja Uhrin Oikeuksien Toteutuminen Suomessa. © Amnesty International.

Amnesty International (2019b) Time for Change: Justice for Rape Survivors in the Nordic Countries. © Amnesty International.

Apulaisoikeuskansleri (2022) Poliisin Menettely Lähisuhdeväkivallan ja Seksuaalirikosten Esitutkinnoissa, OKV/325/70/2022-OKV-5 [Online]. Available at: https://oikeuskansleri.fi/documents/1428954/107303577/julkaistu_ratkaisu_poliisin_menettely_lahisuhdevakivallan_ja_seksuaalirikosten_esitutkinnoissa_OKV_325_70_2022.pdf/503278f5-073f-a36a-6592-aac8f0ac56d3/julkaistu_ratkaisu_poliisin_menettely_lahisuhdevakivallan_ja_seksuaalirikosten_esitutkinnoissa_OKV_325_70_2022.pdf?t=1669283151219 (Accessed: 16 February 2023).

B 1013-09 (2009) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogstodomstolen/avgoranden/2009/38388/> (Accessed: 23 February 2023).

B 1200-19 (2019) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogstodomstolen/avgoranden/2019/21142/> (Accessed: 23 February 2023).

B 1432-16 (2016) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogstodomstolen/avgoranden/2016/35798/> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

B 1867-09 (2009) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogstodomstolen/avgoranden/2009/38388/> (Accessed: 23 February 2023).

B 2862-20 (2020) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogstodomstolen/avgoranden/2021/88982/> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

B 3277-15 (2015) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogstodomstolen/avgoranden/2015/36117/> (Accessed: 23 February 2023).

B 6041-20 (2020) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogstodomstolen/avgoranden/2021/95996/> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

B 6401-21 (2021) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogsta-domstolen/avgoranden/2022/109068/> (Accessed: 23 February 2023).

B 779-21 (2021) *Supreme Court of Sweden* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/hogsta-domstolen/avgoranden/2022/112350/> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

Basow, S. A. and Minieri, A. (2011) ‘“You Owe Me”: Effects of Date Cost, Who Pays, Participant Gender, and Rape Myth Beliefs on Perceptions of Rape’, *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 26(3), pp. 479-497. doi: 10.1177/0886260510363421.

Bieneck, S. and Krahe, B. (2011) ‘Blaming the Victim and Exonerating the Perpetrator in Cases of Rape and Robbery: Is There a Double Standard?’, *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 26(9), pp. 1785-1797. doi: 10.1177/0886260510372945.

British Society of Criminology (BSC) (2015) *Statement of Ethics*. Available at: <http://www.britsocrim.org/ethics/> (Accessed: 15 February 2023).

British Sociological Association (BSA) (2017) *Statement of Ethical Practice*. Available at: https://www.britsoc.co.uk/media/24310/bsa_statement_of_ethical_practice.pdf (Accessed: 15 February 2023).

Brooks, L. (2023) ‘Sexual Assault Survivors Welcome Scottish Plans to Scrap ‘Not Proven’ Verdict’, *The Guardian*, 26 April. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2023/apr/26/scottish-ministers-publish-radical-plan-to-overhaul-handling-of-sexual-offences> (Accessed: 26 April 2023).

Brottsförebyggande Rådet (Brå) (2022) *Sexual Offences*. Available at: <https://bra.se/bra-in-english/home/crime-and-statistics/sexual-offences.html> (Accessed: 18 February 2023).

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union 2012. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT> (Accessed: 27 February 2023).

Clark, T., Foster, L., Sloan, L., and Bryman, A. (2021) *Bryman’s Social Research Methods*, 6th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Constitution of Finland 1999/731, c. 2. Available at: <https://finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/1999/19990731?search%5Bpika%5D=perustuslaki&search%5Btype%5D=pika> (Accessed: 17 April 2023).

Council of Europe (2011) *Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (Istanbul Convention)*. Available at: <https://rm.coe.int/168008482e> (Accessed: 25 October 2022).

Cowan, G. (2000) 'Women's Hostility Toward Women and Rape and Sexual Harassment Myths', *Violence Against Women*, 6(3), pp. 238-246.

Criminal Code of Finland 1889/39, c. 20. Available at: <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/1889/18890039001#L20> (Accessed: 17 January 2023).

Criminal Code of Sweden 1962/700, c. 6. Available at: https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/brottsbalk-1962700_sfs-1962-700#K6 (Accessed: 17 January 2023).

Crowther-Dowey, C. and Fussey, P. (2013) *Researching Crime: Approaches, Methods and Application*. Palgrave Macmillan: Hampshire.

Diener, E. and Crandall, R. (1978) *Ethics in Social and Behavioral Research*, Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.

Egan, R. and Wilson, J. C. (2012) 'Rape Victims' Attitudes to Rape Myth Acceptance', *Psychiatry, Psychology, and Law*, 19(3), pp. 345-357. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13218719.2011.585128>.

European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) (2014) *Violence Against Women: An EU-Wide Survey* [Online]. Available at: https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2014-vaw-survey-main-results-apr14_en.pdf (Accessed: 12 February 2023).

Grubb, A. and Harrower, J. (2008) 'Attribution of Blame in Cases of Rape: An Analysis of Participant Gender, Type of Rape and Perceived Similarity to the Victim', *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 13(5), pp. 396-405. doi: 10.1016/j.avb.2008.06.006.

Grubb, A. and Turner, E. (2012) 'Attribution of Blame in Rape Cases: A Review of the Impact of Rape Myth Acceptance, Gender Role Conformity and Substance Use on Victim Blaming', *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 17(5), pp. 443-452, doi: 10.1016/j.avb.2012.06.002.

HE 13/2022 vp (2022) *Hallituksen Esitys Eduskunnalle Seksuaalirikoksia Koskevaksi Lainsäädännöksi* [Online]. Available at: https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/HallituksenEsitys/Sivut/HE_13+2022.aspx (Accessed: 18 January 2023) (Governmental Proposal [GP] 13/2022).

Honkatukia, P. (2001) 'Rough Sex? Understandings of Rape in Finnish Police Reports', *Journal of Scandinavian Studies in Criminology and Crime Prevention*, 2(1), pp. 15-30.

Immonen-Räihä, P., Klami, R., Bildjuschkin, K., Rantanen, T., Koskinen, K., Taiminen, T., Kauhava, L., and Tunturi, T. (2011) 'Equality for Rape Victims: Developing Pathways in Southwest Finland', *Journal of Management & Marketing in Healthcare*, 4(3), pp. 168-173. doi: 10.1179/1753304X11Y.0000000008.

Isotalo, A. (2022) 'Poliisien Tulkintoja Suostumuksesta ja Seksuaaliväkivallasta Nuorten Seurustelusuhhteissa', *Janus Sosiaalipolitiikan ja Sosiaalityön Aikakauslehti*, 30(3), pp. 269-288. doi: <https://doi.org/10.30668/janus.114709>.

Jokila, H. and Niemi, J. (2020) 'Rape Law and Coercive Circumstances', in Heinskou, M. B., Skilbrei, M-L., and Stefansen, K. (eds.) *Rape in the Nordic Countries*, Routledge: New York, pp. 120-136.

Keller, J., Mendes, K., and Ringrose, J. (2018) 'Speaking 'Unspeakable Things': Documenting Digital Feminist Responses to Rape Culture', *Journal of Gender Studies*, 27(1), pp. 22-36. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09589236.2016.1211511>.

KKO:2014:91 (2014) R2013/688 *Finlex* [Online]. Available at: <https://finlex.fi/fi/oikeus/kko/kko/2014/20140091> (Accessed: 22 February 2023).

KKO:2019:55 (2019) R2017/787 *Finlex* [Online]. Available at: <https://finlex.fi/fi/oikeus/kko/kko/2019/20190055> (Accessed: 22 February 2023).

KKO:2019:78 (2019) R2018/84 *Finlex* [Online]. Available at: <https://finlex.fi/fi/oikeus/kko/kko/2019/20190078> (Accessed: 22 February 2023).

KKO:2019:84 (2019) R2018/550 *Finlex* [Online]. Available at: <https://finlex.fi/fi/oikeus/kko/kko/2019/20190084> (Accessed: 22 February 2023).

KKO:2021:31 (2021) R2020/171 *Supreme Court of Finland* [Online]. Available at: <https://korkeinoikeus.fi/fi/index/ennakkopaatokset/kko202131.html> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

KKO:2021:44 (2021) R2020/82 *Supreme Court of Finland* [Online]. Available at: <https://korkeinoikeus.fi/fi/index/ennakkopaatokset/kko202144.html> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

KKO:2022:50 (2022) R2021/106 *Supreme Court of Finland* [Online]. Available at: <https://korkeinoikeus.fi/fi/index/ennakkopaatokset/qltbx6rea.html> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

KKO:2022:71 (2022) R2021/326 *Supreme Court of Finland* [Online]. Available at: <https://www.korkeinoikeus.fi/fi/index/ennakkopaatokset/kko202271.html> (Accessed: 30 March 2023).

Kolttola, I. A. and Näsi, M. 2022, *Suomalaiset Väkivallan ja Omaisuusrikosten Kohteena 2021: Kansallisen Rikosuhritutkimuksen Tuloksia*. Katsauksia [Online]. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/348246> (14 February 2023).

Lappi-Seppälä, T. (2012) 'Criminology, Crime and Criminal Justice in Finland', *European Journal of Criminology*, 9(2), pp. 206-222. doi: 10.1177/147737081142372.

Malin, T., Vauhkonen, T., and Latvala, A. (2022) 'Seksuaalirikokset' in Kolttola, I. *Rikollisuustilanne 2021: Rikollisuuskehitys Tilastojen ja Tutkimusten Valossa*, Katsauksia [Online]. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/352549> (Accessed: 14 February 2023).

McGregor, J. (2016) *Is It Rape?: On Acquaintance Rape and Taking Women's Consent Seriously*, Routledge: New York.

Möller, A., Söndergaard, H. P., & Helström, L. (2017) 'Tonic Immobility During Sexual Assault – A Common Reaction Predicting Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder and Severe Depression', *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica Scandinavica*, 96(8), pp. 932-938. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/aogs.13174>.

O'Neal, E. N. and Hayes, B. E. (2020) "'A Rape Is a Rape, Regardless of What the Victim Was Doing at the Time": Detective Views on How "Problematic" Victims Affect Sexual Assault Case Processing', *Criminal Justice Review*, 45(1), pp. 26-44. doi: 10.177/0734016819842639.

Oikeuspoliittinen Tutkimuslaitos (2012) *Selvityksiä Raiskausrikoksista*. Oikeusministeriön Selvityksiä ja Ohjeita [Online]. Available at: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-259-186-9> (Accessed: 16 February 2023).

Payne, D. L., Lonsway, K. A., and Fitzgerald, L. F. (1999) 'Rape Myth Acceptance: Exploration of Its Structure and Its Measurement Using the *Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale*', *Journal of Research in Personality*, 33(1), pp. 27-68.

Randall, M. (2010) 'Sexual Assault Law, Credibility, and "Ideal Victims": Consent, Resistance, and Victim Blaming', *Canadian Journal of Women and the Law*, 22(2), pp. 397-433. doi: 10.3138/cjwl.22.2.397.

Rees, G. (2010) 'It is Not for Me to Say Whether Consent Was Given or Not': Forensic Medical Examiners' Construction of 'Neutral Reports' in Rape Cases', *Social & Legal Studies*, 19(3), pp. 371-386. doi: 10.1177/0964663910362291.

Ridderstedt, M. (2018) 'Unga Män Mer Negativa till Samtyckeslagen', *Sverigers Radio*, 8 November. Available at: <https://sverigesradio.se/artikel/7086377> (Accessed: 25 February 2023).

Stefansen, K. (2020) 'Understanding unwanted sexual touching: A situational approach', in Heinskou, M. B., Skilbrei, M-L., and Stefansen, K. (eds.) *Rape in the Nordic Countries*, Routledge: New York, pp. 49-65.

Suostumus2018 (2023) *Kampanja*. Available at: <http://suostumus2018.fi/sv/info/> (Accessed: 25 February).

Supreme Court of Finland (2020) *Functions*. Available at: <https://korkeinoikeus.fi/en/index/supremecourt/functions.html#> (Accessed: 4 April 2023).

Supreme Court of Sweden (2022) *Role and Mission*. Available at: <https://www.domstol.se/en/supreme-court/about-the-supreme-court/about-us/role-and-mission/> (Accessed: 4 April 2023).

Tadros, V. (2006) 'Rape Without Consent', *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, 26(3), pp. 515-543. doi: 10.1093/ojls/gql016.

Tilastokeskus (2021) *Raiskausrikosten Käsitteilyn Keston Mediaani 226 Päivää Vuonna 2021*. Available at: <https://stat.fi/julkaisu/cl3eaq0vx2rpz0bulqa1g4qrh> (Accessed: 17 February 2023).

Tilastokeskus (2022) *Rikos- ja Pakkokeinotilasto*. Available at: <https://stat.fi/tilasto/rpk> (Accessed: 17 February 2023).

Tilastokeskus (2023) *Concepts: Solved Offence*. Available at: https://www.stat.fi/meta/kas/selvitetty_riko_en.html (Accessed: 17 February 2023).

van der Bruggen, M. and Grubb, A. (2014) 'A Review of the Literature Relating to Rape Victim Blaming: An Analysis of the Impact of Observer and Victim Characteristics on Attribution of Blame in Rape Cases', *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 19(5), pp. 523-531. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2014.07.008>.

Yar, M. (2018) 'Doing Criminological Research Online', in Davies, P. and Francis, P. (eds.) *Doing criminological research*, 3rd ed. Los Angeles: Sage. pp. 413-432.